

the fertility change of Zhenong 1S. This indicates that the change from sterility to fertility for Zhenong 1S is stable and clear under field conditions in Hangzhou (35° 05' N).

The sterility of W6154S, which is being widely used for two-line hybrid

rices in China, is primarily controlled by higher temperature (29.7 °C) and not by longer photoperiod (Table 2). Therefore it has limited use in hybrid seed production.

The self-sterility rate of Zhenong 1S under long photoperiod (14.75 h) is above 99.7%, regardless of temperature. Under

short photoperiod (13.25 h), the self-seed setting rate of Zhenong 1S increases as temperature falls. This confirms that under long photoperiod, Zhenong 1S is completely sterile, but fertility is induced under short photoperiod (13.25 h) with lower temperature (25.7 °C). ■

Evaluation of male sterile lines with Honglien cytosterility

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A 4 × 4 incomplete diallel cross involving four male sterile lines of Honglien-type Cong-Guang 41 A, Zhao-Tai A, Qing-Lu A, and Qing-Er A, and restorer lines Te-Qing 2, Qi-Ja-Zhan, Zhen-Gui-Ai, and Qing-Lu-Ai was carried out in 1990 to study the combining ability of the male sterile lines and their biological properties.

We planted the 16 hybrids in a randomized block design with three replications in the early season (from Mar

to Jul 1991) under irrigated conditions. Sixty seedlings were transplanted at 16.7 × 20-cm spacing in each plot.

Cong-Guang 41 A was a good general combiner for plant height, individual plant yield, 1,000-grain weight, total spikelets per panicle, number of full grains per panicle, and seed set percentage, but not for number of effective panicles per hill (Table 1).

Qing-Er A was a poor combiner for seed set percentage, suggesting that it was not easily restored.

Cong-Guang 41 A was tallest; Qing-Er A was shortest. Cong-Guang 41 A had large panicles and few spikelets enclosed in the leaf sheath. Qing-Er A was high in stigma exertion rate, followed by Cong-Guang 41 A (Table 2).

Cong-Guang 41 A appears to be a superior male sterile line compared with the other lines. ■

L-proline-mediated, high-frequency regeneration in rice cultivar IR66

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We initiated calli cultures from seeds of rice cultivar IR66. The dehulled seeds were washed with distilled water and then surface-sterilized in 0.1% HgCl₂ solution for 5 min. Seeds were washed three times with sterile distilled water and placed in 150-ml Erlenmeyer flasks containing 30 ml of solid medium. The culture medium for calli induction consisted of basal Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium supplemented with 2,4-D (2 mg/liter), coconut water (10%, vol/vol), and sucrose (3%, wt/vol). The cultures were incubated at 26 ± 2 °C under continuous light of about 2,000 lx. The calli obtained were subcultured on calli induction medium at an interval of 21 d.

After two subcultures, calli were transferred to medium that had L-proline incorporated into it at 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, and 1.0 mg/liter and incubated for 21 d. The proline-treated calli were then transferred to regeneration medium composed of basal MS salts supplemented with IAA (1.0 mg/liter) and BAP (0.3 mg/liter).

Green spots appeared in the calli while being incubated for 21 d. The spots developed slowly and there were not as many in the calli not treated with proline. We transferred the spots to either solid or liquid medium having the

Table 1. General combining ability effects of the male sterile lines. Guangdong, China, 1991.

Male sterile line	General combining ability (%)						
	Plant ht	Individual plant yield	1000-grain wt	Total spikelets/panicle	Full grains/panicle	Seed set	Effective panicles/hill
Qing-Lu A	2.46	6.21	0.50	-3.68	-3.73	1.92	4.73
Qing-Er A	-8.42	-17.10	-4.63	-9.34	-16.58	-6.78	4.62
Zhao-Tai A	2.31	1.54	2.14	-0.83	0.61	0.72	-1.98
Cong-Guang 41 A	3.64	9.26	1.94	13.84	19.67	4.14	-9.01
LSD (P = 0.05)	4.51	0.99	1.28	11.98	11.70	5.33	1.88

Table 2. Agronomic characters of the male sterile lines. Guangdong, China, 1991.

Male sterile line	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Length (cm) of panicles enclosed in leaf sheath	Spikelets enclosed/panicle (no.)	Leaves/main culm (no.)	Stigma exertion rate (%)
Qing-Lu A	85.3	10.3	148.0	4.56	3.8	15.11	23.47
Qing-Er A	69.0	9.0	128.2	4.61	4.0	15.54	65.38
Zhao-Tai A	84.0	10.0	117.8	5.09	5.1	14.50	32.16
Cong-Guang 41 A	93.0	7.3	210.5	5.26	1.9	15.00	43.16
LSD (P = 0.05)	5.34	2.4	13.6	ns ^a	2.3	0.78	8.56

^aNonsignificant.

Regeneration capacity of IR66 calli as influenced by different treatments.

Treatment	Regeneration ^a	
	Solid medium	Liquid medium
Control	16-35 (15)	16-35 (15)
L-proline : 0.1 mg/liter	Clusters of small plantlets without further growth	30-50 (100-150)
L-proline : 0.3 mg/liter	Clusters of small plantlets without further growth	30-50 (100-150)
L-proline : 0.5 mg/liter	No regeneration	No regeneration
L-proline : 1.0 mg/liter	No regeneration	No regeneration

^aFigures in parentheses are the number of regenerated plantlets per culture vessel.

same composition as that of the regeneration medium. Filter paper was used to transfer the spots to the liquid medium.

Untreated calli not only developed green spots slowly, but their regeneration capacity was also less than that of the treated calli (see table). Results were similar when we transferred untreated calli to liquid regeneration medium. We observed a very high frequency (30-50%, 100-150 plantlets per culture vessel) of regeneration capacity in calli treated with low concentrations (0.1 or 0.3 mg/liter) of L-proline and transferred to liquid medium. High proline-treated calli, however, failed to regenerate on either liquid or solid media. ■

Performance of Punjab CMS lines in Cuttack, India

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We grew cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines PMS1 A to PMS10 A from a wild abortive source and their isonuclear maintainers from Kapurthala, Punjab, in the field during 1991 dry season (DS) and wet season (WS). The experiment was part of a collaborative project with the Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India. We recorded pollen sterility, spikelet sterility in bagged panicles, plant height, days to 50% flowering, and panicle exertion from unreplicated rows of 30 plants for each of the CMS and maintainer lines.

Of the 10 CMS lines, PMS3 A, PMS4 A, PMS5 A, PMS8 A, and PMS10 A were completely pollen sterile, had reduced white anthers, and did not set any seed in bagged panicles in either season (see table). PMS1 A was completely sterile during DS and PMS7 A was sterile during WS. PMS2 A, PMS6 A, and PMS9 A were unstable.

All CMS and maintainer lines were of medium duration. Most of the CMS lines flowered 2-4 d later, had shorter plants and poorer panicle exertion than their maintainers (see table), perhaps because of the influence of their cytoplasmic

Evaluation of Punjab CMS and maintainer lines at CRRRI, Cuttack, Orissa, India, 1991 DS and WS.

CMS or maintainer line	Pedigree of B line	Pollen sterility (%)		Spikelet fertility (%)		Plant height (cm)		Days to 50% flowering		Panicle exertion (%)
		DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	
PMS1 A		100	76.0	0	21.4	74	59	105	92	64.3
PMS1 B	Phulpattes 72/Jaya	-	-	79.3	84.1	88	83	105	89	100
PMS2 A		95	15.9	2.8	77.6	74	117	106	96	84.3
PMS2 B	Phulpattes 72/ Mutant 15	-	-	79.9	82.6	89	121	105	93	100
PMS3 A		100	100	0	0	77	63	106	94	72.1
PMS3 B	Basmati Mutant	-	-	83.0	87.6	90	83	104	92	100
PMS4 A		100	100	0	0	77	67	109	103	77.5
PMS4 B	IR8/Sigadis//NS200	-	-	67.9	79.4	83	78	109	100	100
PMS5 A		100	100	0	0	67	80	110	105	79.8
PMS5 B	PB134/Pb 133	-	-	79.3	75.2	85	85	109	105	100
PMS6 A		81.7	70.8	20.4	24.0	71	76	111	106	97.2
PMS6 B	PB134/Pb 133	-	-	68.9	85.1	89	82	110	105	100
PMS7 A		75.7	100	30.4	0	71	62	111	104	73.6
PMS7 B	IR305-3-17-13/ IR661-1-140-3	-	-	74.0	80.9	88	78	107	102	100
PMS8 A		100	100	0	0	79	80	105	105	76.9
PMS8 B	IR747-82-6-3/ IR665-40-6-3	-	-	76.7	71.8	91	85	102	104	100
PMS9 A		71.3	70.0	10.9	10.4	90	76	106	103	83.7
PMS9 B	PAU169-49-3-1-1/ PAU29-295-3-28	-	-	85.5	84.9	94	84	102	103	100
PMS10 A		100	100	0	0	74	69	107	91	78.5
PMS10 B	RP2B-849	-	-	71.8	68.4	87	74	103	90	100

factor. CMS lines were free from major diseases and pests.

Stable PMS lines PMS3 A, PMS4 A, PMS5 A, PMS8 A, and PMS10 A may be useful in developing hybrid rice for

the shallow rainfed ecosystem of eastern India because of their semitall stature, stiff straw, and medium duration. ■